

Infrared Spectra of Some Heterocyclic Keto-methylene Compounds. Part I. Amide-carbonyl, Enolic, and Aromatic Bands

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Several keto-methylene compounds have been prepared and their IR spectra studied with respect to (1) the effect of conjugation on the amide $>C=O$ bond (on formation of styryl compounds), (2) effect on the enolic character of the amide $>C=O$ bond (on formation of styryl compounds), and (3) characteristic frequency changes on introduction of styryl group. As a result of these structural changes, characteristic frequencies are observed in the regions 5μ to 6μ , 8μ to 9μ , 13μ to 14μ , and 14μ to 15μ . On the basis of the data, some generalisations on structure-spectra correlation are discussed.

In the present investigation, several keto-methylene compounds have been prepared and their IR spectra studied. The following structural changes have been investigated:

- (i) Effect of conjugation on the amide $>C=O$ bond by formation of styryl compounds.
- (ii) Characteristic frequencies of styryl group.
- (iii) Effect on the enolic character of the amide $>C=O$ on formation of styryl compounds.

As a result of these structural changes, characteristic frequencies are observed in the following regions: 5μ to 6μ , 8μ to 9μ , 13μ to 14μ , 14μ to 15μ .

Characteristic Changes in the Region 5μ to 6μ

From the shifts of the carbonyl band on formation of benzylidene compounds, the relative acidities of the various hetero-aromatic keto-methylene compounds, studied in the present work, have been evaluated. The relative electron-attracting property of hetero-aromatic molecules from IR spectra has been previously observed¹ with compounds of the type:

The $>C=O$ stretching frequency increases and the C-N stretching frequency decreases as the ring becomes increasingly electron-attracting, i.e., pyrrole < imidazole < triazole

>tetrazole. Katritzky and Jones² found that in compounds of the type:

the heterocyclic ring and the >C=O group compete for the lone electron pair on the nitrogen atom and the >C=O stretching frequency is increased with rise in electron-accepting power of the heterocyclic ring.

The frequencies of the amide-carbonyl bands of the various nuclei, studied in the present investigation, and the shifts, observed on conjugation by formation of benzylidene compounds, are shown in Table I along with their melting points.

TABLE I

Compounds.	M.P.	Characteristic frequencies in 5 μ to 6 μ region.	Shift.
1. 2-Phenylimino-4-thiazolidone ³	179°	5.95 μ or 1682 cm^{-1}	} 2 cm^{-1}
2. 5-Benzylidene compound of (1)	256-57°	5.96 μ or 1680 cm^{-1}	
3. 3-Phenylthiohydantoin ⁴	248°(d)	5.69 μ or 1758 cm^{-1}	} 18 cm^{-1}
4. 5-Benzylidene compound of (3)	203°	5.75 μ or 1740 cm^{-1}	
5. 3-Phenylrhodanine ⁵	103°	5.76 μ or 1735 cm^{-1}	} 10 cm^{-1}
6. Benzylidene compound of (5)	184°	5.8 μ or 1725 cm^{-1}	
7. Thiobarbituric acid ⁶	250°(d)	5.8 μ or 1725 cm^{-1}	} 65 cm^{-1}
8. 5-Benzylidene compound of (7)	280°	6.02 μ or 1660 cm^{-1}	
9. 4,4'-Benzylidene-bis-(3,4-dimethyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone) ⁷ (unisolable pyrazolone)	162°	5.93 μ or 1715 cm^{-1}	} 28 cm^{-1}
10. 4-Benzylidene-3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone ⁸	107°	5.93 μ or 1687 cm^{-1}	
11. 3-Phenyl-5-iso-oxazolone ⁹	152°	5.54 μ or 1805 cm^{-1}	} 62 cm^{-1}
12. 4-Benzylidene compound (11)	190°	5.74 μ or 1743 cm^{-1}	

N.B. Benzylidene derivatives were prepared from the parent compounds by treatment with benzaldehyde and fused sodium acetate in acetic acid medium. (d) denotes decomposition.

The electron drift in the system;

acts in opposition to that in the system:

2. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 2067.
3. Ramachandra *et al.*, *Anal. Chem.*, 1955, **27**, 1734.
4. Rout *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, **77**, 2427.
5. Bailey and McPherson, *ibid.*, 1916, **38**, 2523.
6. Rout *et al.*, *J. Sci. Ind. Res.* 1955, **14B**, 13.
7. B.D.H. L.R., recrystallised from acetic acid.
8. Rout *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1963, **40**, 833.
9. *Idem, ibid.*, 1961, **38**, 893.
10. Rabe, *Ber.*, 1887, **30**, 1614.
11. Lecher *et al.*, *J. Phys. Chem.* 1955, **59**, 619.

Where the latter predominates, the amidic character is conspicuous and the characteristic frequencies are observed near 1667 cm^{-1} ($6.0\ \mu$), but where the former predominates, the amide-carbonyl band is shifted towards lower wave-length region and approximates to that of the ketonic carbonyl. This explains why iso-oxazolone, where amidic character is minimum, absorbs at $5.54\ \mu$ region. In the case of thiobarbituric acid, a saturated six-membered ring compound with no ring strain, the amide-carbonyl band is in a lower frequency region ($5.9\ \mu$) than iso-oxazolone, though both possess comparable acidity. Pyrazolone compounds having enolisable carbonyl group provide a complex absorption pattern in the $5.8\ \mu$ to $6\ \mu$ region. Therefore, measurement of the carbonyl band of pyrazolone was made on the unenolisable 4, 4'-benzylidene-bis-(3,4-dimethyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone). Pyrazolone absorbs at $5.83\ \mu$, which is higher than that of rhodanine or thiohydantoin, though it contains the same group $\text{Ph}=\text{N}-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}$, probably due to its conjugation with $-\text{C}=\text{N}-$. The lowest value for the amide-carbonyl group frequency of thiazolidone is expected as it possesses maximum amidic character. The effect of conjugation is to favour the polarisation of the keto-methylene carbonyl group:

and suppress or retard the polarisation of the amide-carbonyl group. The extent of the bathochromic shift is therefore dependent on the magnitude of these competing effects.

The maximum bathochromic shift of 65 cm^{-1} is observed in the case of thiobarbituric acid, which is known to have maximum acidity. Iso-oxazolone having acidity of the same order shows bathochromic shift of 62 cm^{-1} . Pyrazolone has less acidity and shows the next lower bathochromic shift of 28 cm^{-1} . The bathochromic shifts of rhodanine and thiohydantoin are nearly of the same order. Conjugation produces little effect on the amide-carbonyl band of the thiazolidone nucleus, perhaps because of its pronounced amidic character.

Characteristic Changes in the Region $8\ \mu$ to $9\ \mu$

Examination of this region in various keto-methylene nuclei shows that where the polarisation of the keto-methylene carbonyl group is greater than that of the amide-carbonyl group, i.e., when enolisation of the $-\text{CH}_2-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}$ is more pronounced, a strong band is found in the $8.5\ \mu$ to $8.7\ \mu$ region. In thiobarbituric acid, the band is at $8.67\ \mu$; in benzylidene-thiobarbituric acid, the $8.67\ \mu$ band is weak and may be due to $=\text{C}-\text{OH}$, formed by slight enolisation of $-\text{NH}-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}$ group. In case of the enolisable compound, 3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone, the strong $8.5\ \mu$ band completely disappears on benzylidene formation.

Characteristic Changes in the Regions $13\ \mu$ - $14\ \mu$ and $14\ \mu$ - $15\ \mu$

On the formation of the styryl compounds, it is generally observed that if the original compound contains the phenyl group, there is a shift towards longer wave-length region of the characteristic aromatic bands and a second band also appears in the higher region. In some cases, there is splitting of the bands, one band appearing in the lower region and another appearing in the higher region. Thus, in the case of rhodanine the band at $13.2\ \mu$ is

split into two bands, 13.15μ and 13.66μ , in benzylidenerhodanine. The 14.45μ band of rhodanine, which may be due both to ring sulphur or the phenyl nucleus, is on condensation with benzaldehyde shifted to a broad band at 14.45μ to 14.65μ . The case of thiazolidone is similar, the band at 13.3μ being resolved into bands at 13.16μ and 13.37μ in styryl-thiazolidone. The band at 14.5μ of thiazolidone undergoes bathochromic shift and forms a broad band at 14.55 to 14.75μ . In the case of pyrazolone and iso-oxazolone, which do not contain any ring sulphur, only shifting to higher wave-length region is observed in both the 13.14μ and 14.15μ regions. Thus in pyrazolone, the bands $12.95\mu(w)$, $13.4\mu(m)$, and $14.17\mu(m)$ are shifted to $13.18\mu(s)$, $13.37\mu(w)$, and $14.6\mu(s)$ respectively. Similarly also in the case of iso-oxazolone, the bands at $13.08\mu(s)$ and $14.42\mu(m)$ are shifted to $13.16\mu(s)$, $13.60\mu(m)$ and $14.35\mu(m)$, $14.62\mu(s)$ respectively.

EXPERIMENTAL

All the samples were taken in nujol mull for the IR observations. The absorption peaks of each compound are shown below.

2-Phenylimino-4-thiazolidone: 5.95(s), 6.08(s), 6.12(s), 6.22(m), 6.37(s), 6.45(m), 6.55(m), 6.61(s), 6.66(s), 6.60(s), 6.74(s), 6.90(s), 7.13(m), 7.57(m), 7.70(w), 7.82(w), 7.90(s), 8.10(s), 8.10(s), 8.32(m), 8.47(s), 11.12(w), 12.05(s), 12.46(m), 13.33(m), 14.50(m).

5-Benzylidene-2-phenylimino-4-thiazolidone: 5.56(s), 6.67(s), 6.10(s), 6.17(s), 6.24(s), 6.44(m), 6.52(m), 5.59(m), 6.68(m), 7.10(w), 7.10(w), 7.80(s), 7.87(m), 8.28(m), 8.41(w), 8.47(m), 11.10(w), 11.50(w), 13.15(m), 13.37(m), 14.55(m), 14.65(m).

3-Phenylrhodanine: 5.76(s), 6.08(w), 6.27(w), 6.44(w), 6.52(w), 6.60(w), 6.68(w), 6.87(m), 7.43(s), 7.58(w), 7.75(m), 8.05(s), 8.13(s), 8.27(m), 8.47(m), 8.56(m), 8.96(m), 9.34(m), 9.47(m), 11.30(m), 12.07(m), 12.74(w), 13.20(m), 14.45(s).

5-Benzylidene-3-phenylrhodanine: 5.80(s), 6.26(m), 6.44(m), 6.52(m), 6.60(m), 6.68(m), 6.93(m), 7.37(m), 8.02(s), 8.52(m), 8.68(m), 12.14(m), 13.15(m), 13.60(m), 14.55(m), 14.65(m).

5-Benzylidene-3-phenylthiohydantion: 5.75(s), 6.02(m), 6.07(m), 6.44(m), 6.52(m), 6.60(m), 6.65(m), 6.68(m), 6.75(m), 6.88(m), 6.93(m), 7.10(m), 8.02(m), 8.35(w), 9.20(w), 10.82(w), 13.05(m), 13.20(m), 13.78(m), 14.18(m), 14.70(s).

3-Phenylthiohydantoin: 5.69(s), 6.00(m), 6.06(m), 6.10(m), 6.43(m), 6.52(s), 6.58(m), 5.88(s), 6.82(s), 7.82(w), 8.35(w).

Thioarbituric acid: 5.80(s), 6.02(m), 6.07(m), 6.45(m), 6.53(m), 6.61(m), 6.65(m), 6.75(m), 6.79(m), 7.02(w), 7.45(s), 7.80(w), 8.03(m), 8.67(s), 8.77(s).

Benzylidenethioarbituric acid: 6.02(s), 6.08(m), 6.45(m), 6.53(m), 5.61(m), 6.65(m), 6.75(m), 6.79(m), 7.02(w), 7.45(s), 7.80(w), 8.03(m), 8.63(w), 8.77(s).

4,4'-Benzylidene-bis-(3,4-dimethyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone): 5.83(s), 6.08(m), 6.26(m), 6.43(m), 6.52(m), 6.60(m), 6.68(m), 6.74(m), 7.32(m), 7.76(m), 8.75(m), 11.02(m), 12.06(m), 13.40(w), 14.17(m).

4. *Benzylidene-3-methyl-1-phenyl-5-pyrazolone*: 5.93(s), 6.24(s), 6.36(m), 6.43(m), 6.52(m), 6.60(w), 6.68(m), 7.32(m), 7.56(s), 8.75(w), 10.02(m), 11.84(m), 13.18(m), 13.37(m), 14.60(s).

3. *Phenyl-5-iso-oxazolone*: 5.54 (s), 6.08 (m), 6.30 (m), 6.45 (m), 6.54 (m), 6.60 (m), 6.75(m), 8.82(s), 11.10(s), 11.40 (s), 13.08(s), 14.42(m).

4. *Benzylidene-3-phenyl-5-iso-oxazolone*: 5.74 (s), 6.17 (s), 6.20 (s), 6.38(m), 6.46(m), 6.70(m), 6.77(m), 7.71(w), 8.20(w), 8.50(w), 9.07(m), 9.17(m), 9.22(s), 10.52(w), 10.62(s), 11.10(s), 12.690(m), 13.05(m), 13.16(s), 13.40(w), 13.60(m), 14.35(s), 14.62(s).

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